

Sustain Sahel

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Main Authors: Moussa Gnissien (UNB), Kalifa Coulibaly (UNB), Hassan Bismarck Nacro (UNB), Laurent Cournac (IRD)

Deliverable 5.1. Meta-analysis of shrubs and trees effects on soil parameters

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1. Executive summary

A database was constituted from 63 references selected from literature on Sahelian agriculture containing trees and shrubs effects on soil parameters. We extracted the information from the literature particularly the treatment vs control effects as shown in the delivered data table in the appendix. . This deliverable presents the initial analysis and the findings from this dataset, which will be enriched throughout the project. First results confirm beneficial effects of trees and shrubs on soil parameters such as carbon and nitrogen contents, cations, soil structure and biological activities. These effects however, show some variation from one publication to the other, depending on the type of soil, climate parameters, and management of ligneous biomass that were applied. This database therefore constitutes a valuable source of knowledge, which will allow partners of the project to test hypotheses on factors that trigger agroforestry systems performance, and which will be used to help designing innovative ligneous species management practices in Sahelian agriculture.

2. Literature review of trees and shrubs impacts on soil parameters in the Sahel

2.1 Objectives

The objective of this literature review and meta-analysis is to capitalize on existing knowledge of the impacts of shrubs and trees on soil parameters in Sahelian and Sudano-Sahelian agricultural systems and therefore on related ecosystem services. This is done through a meta-analysis combining references from classical literature data bases and grey literature hosted in the national research centers of participating countries.

A seminal work has been published by Felix et al, comprised 47 references in which quantitative data were found as useable for meta-analysis. Our objective is (i) to complement this database with relevant data from the area, and complement this original work with peer-reviewed and grey literature (ii) give a more comprehensive view of agroforestry (incl. shrub) influence on soil parameters, and processes underlining them, (iii) constitute a baseline of data to which the experiments and surveys conducted in the project could refer in order to better understand observed effects

2.2. Methodology

This literature review involved electronic media consisting of bachelor's degree reports, engineering theses, master's degree, doctoral thesis, books and scientific articles published in journals with or without impact factor. The literature referencing sites consulted are: the website of the Nazi Boni University, the site of Research4life, Google Scholar and Web of Science. Around 350 references were retrieved in total, we then analyzed these references to extract those in which quantitative assessment of soil parameters, and suitable comparisons with control situations were made, in order to gather data useable for meta-analysis. 63 references were retained at this stage. The software "Ligneux du Sahel" and internet searches were used to specify the names of the families to which the various tree and shrub species studied belong, as well as the origin of these species (native or exotic) when this was not specified in the manuscript. In order to be able to analyze the effects of trees and shrubs on the different soil properties, the salient

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results (effect on soil parameters according to the different treatments) of each manuscript were entered into the database.

A previous work of this kind was performed by Félix, G.F., Scholberg, J.M.S., Clermont-Dauphin, C. et al. (2018) on „Enhancing agroecosystem productivity with woody perennials in semi-arid West Africa. A meta-analysis“.

The database in its more recent state now covers 92 references, which is twice the number of what was gathered in Felix et al (47 references). Felix et al 's work essentially focused on the question of ramial wood amendment, with few differentiation of other agroforestry practice. Our work is aimed to complement this aspect.

In particular, **diversity of agroforestry management practices and interactions with livestock was poorly covered**. Our final goal in the project is to work on data confrontation between data dealing with soil aspects in WP5, data on agroforestry practices and effects on yield/environmental performances in WP4 and data on tree/shrub usage with livestock in order to get a deeper insight and innovative view on these interactions. This is the work in progress beyond the current literature analysis.

2.3. Main findings

2.3.1 Data collected

Contexts of the studies

The data collected on the effects of trees and shrubs on soil properties came from the following countries: Burkina Faso (45% of the work), Senegal (35%), Niger (6%), Mali (6%), Benin (5%) and Nigeria (3%) (Fig.1).

Figure 1: Source country for literature retained for analysis.

Three types of trials were conducted to assess the impact of ligneous species on soils on-farm (52% of the work), on-station (40%) and in greenhouses or *in vitro* (8%). Most of the species were native species (87%) and 13% were exotic species (mainly legumes) grouped into 15 families. The most studied families

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were Caesalpiniaceae (41%) with the species *Piliostigma reticulatum* (shrub) and *Parkia biglobosa* (tree), Combretaceae (21%) mainly represented by *Guiera senegalensis* (shrub) and Sapotaceae (17%) represented by *Vitellaria paradoxa* (tree). The management were coppicing (75% of cases), pruning (19%) and pollarding (6%). Coppicing was practiced on shrubs, pruning concerned both shrubs and trees, and pollarding was specific to trees. Mulching (79% of cases) and burial (21%) were the most common ways to manage tree and shrub biomass applied to soil in the trials where this was specified.

The trials were conducted on 11 major soil types according to the WRB classification, of which Lixisols (43% of soils) and Arenosols (16% of soils) were the most numerous.

Depths of soil samples taken

Soil samples were taken at several depths, but the majority were taken between 0-20 cm (67%).

Physical properties of the soil

The results on the physical properties concerned the granulometry (10 %), the bulk density (14 %), the temperature (5 %), the porosity (3 %), the hydraulic conductivity (5 %), the moisture content (16 %), useful water reserve (5%), infiltration rate (11%), sportivity (2%), drainage (2%), runoff (2%), ant galleries (3%), earthworm castings (3%) and termite casts (3%).

Soil chemical properties

Results on soil chemical properties included pH_{water} (32% of results) and pH_{KCl} (10%), organic matter (13%), organic carbon (43%), total nitrogen (40%), C/N (11%), N/P (2%), C/P (3%), total phosphorus (17%), total potassium (5%), inorganic nitrogen (6%), NH_4^+ ions (6%), NO_3^- (5%), inorganic phosphorus (3%), available phosphorus (25%), extractable phosphorus (2%), available potassium (5%). They also included exchangeable bases such as Ca^{2+} (11%), Mg^{2+} (11%), K^+ (11%), Na^+ (8%), Mn^{2+} (2%), CEC (10%) and the sum of exchangeable bases SBE (2%).

Biological properties of the soil

The results on biological properties concern the macrofauna population (effects depicted in the physical properties section), nematodes (2%), microbial biomass (8%), arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi (3%), fungi (3%) and bacteria (3%). Results on biological activities included CO_2 release (10% of the work), induced basal respiration (6%), metabolic quotient (2%), enzyme activities such as β -glucosidase (3%), acid phosphatase (2%), chitinase (2%) and urease (2%).

2.3.1 Influence of ligneous species on relevant soil parameters

The literature gathered shows a somehow scattered way of appraising tree/shrub related impacts on soil parameters, and these parameters have often been measured in different ways, making inter-comparisons difficult. Moreover, the documented studies encompass a wide range of tree species selection and management practices. For instance, trees may be implanted inside the fields, or biomass from surrounding trees brought to the field as amendment, the ligneous species may be regularly pruned or not, tree influence may be combined with fertilizer input or not. We are still building on the rich and diverse (complex) information that results from the combination of these factors. Below we discuss some of the observations on common soil quality parameters. Soil organic matter/carbon content

Soil organic matter is a well-known proxy of soil fertility, associated with soil stability, mineral and water retention, and biological activity stimulation. Most of the studies found that ligneous species presence led to an increase of soil C (or organic matter - OM) content in the vicinity of the tree/shrub, which consequently increased the C/OM status of the whole field. This characteristic is well documented in the literature gathered in our area as well (Fig.2)

Figure 2: Effect of tree and shrub presence on soil carbon content.

C enrichment under tree/shrub canopy typically ranged from 20 to 75% compared to control treatment where no tree/shrub was present. Impact of mulch from distant trees was more limited, and in some rare cases had a neutral or slightly negative effect (Refs 9-17-33 for instance).

Nitrogen content

In line with OM content improvements in soils, N content was also increased in the soil by the presence of trees and shrubs.

Figure 3: Impact of ligneous species on soil nitrogen content, grouped by soil type

Interestingly, the most sandy and OM depleted sols (arenosols, lixisols) were the ones that benefited most from ligneous species influence in terms of nitrogen content.

Phosphorus content

P is another major element for which availability is often severely limited in the Sahel. P availability in regards to to shrub presence has been documented in some studies in the Sahel area. The results are less consistent than those concerning C content. There are reports of P status improvement due to presence of trees or amendments with ligneous biomass, but impoverishments have also been reported. Further investigation is needed to understand contexts in which an improvement of P status is triggered by agroforestry systems. These analyses gave a much more contrasted view than the one performed in previous work by Felix et al.

Figure 4: Influence of tree/shrub on soil available P status, in all references where it was documented

Other chemical parameters

These were not addressed in previous work. SustainSAHEL feels that these might be crucial to understand some of the enhancing effects linked with tree/shrub presence.

An interesting feature of tree/shrub impact on Sahelian soils is the widely acknowledged impact on pH, which is increased in the vast majority of cases. This is expected in relation with OM content increase. Presence of trees or input of ligneous organic matter led to a pH increase in the majority of reported cases (Figure 5). Surprisingly, this effect was not clearly dependent on initial pH status of the soil, whereas one could have expected the relative impact to be much higher on acidic soils than on neutral or alkaline ones.

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Figure 5: Effect of tree/shrub presence on soil pH, in function of soil control pH status.

In line with this, available cations contents, which were reported in a few references, increased as well. These elements are extremely important for crop fertility, and very often depleted in the sandy and lixiviated context that characterizes most Sahelian soils. An example is given below with data on calcium. This phenomenon of enrichment in soil cations at tree vicinity is referred to as potentially having two origins: (i) deep soil uplift of minerals through the root system of trees/shrubs and restitution through litterfall for instance, and (ii) wind trapping of dust and air borne particles by trees/shrub canopies and deposition.

Figure 6: Enhancement in soil Calcium (Ca^{2+}) content from the references in which it was measured

Soil physical parameters, structure, stability

Tree/shrub influence was reported by all studies to have a beneficial impact on soil structural parameters (structure, macrofauna-related soil porosity, aggregate formation, etc.). An integrative parameter depicting this is bulk density, which aggregates in situ soil structuration (indeed, structuration improves soil porosity

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and air circulation, which lowers bulk density of soil cores). Bulk density is consistently decreased in presence of trees and shrubs in a wide range of systems and regions, which depicts an improvement in soil structuration. The bulk density of soil was consistently decreased under tree or shrub influence, with only one exception observed under shea tree (*Vitellaria paradoxa*) in ref 24.

Figure 7: Influence of tree family/species on soil bulk density.

Biological parameters

Biological parameters assessments in a rigorous way (i.e. vs control) are rather scarce because of difficulty involving the analysis of samples. Parameter such as microorganisms presence, microbial biomass, faunal presence or activity, were systematically increased in the presence of ligneous species, which is not surprising as these parameters are essentially dependent on soil OM content. An illustration of that can be given by the reports in figure 8 which shows in a variety of situations an enhancement of abundance in fungi and bacteria in shrub-influenced vs control situation (non-rhizospheric soil in ref 19).

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Figure 8: Effect of shrub influence on fungi and bacteria numbers in soil.

2.4. Conclusion and perspectives

This analysis of current literature clearly points out a beneficial effect of ligneous species presence in agricultural systems on a wide variety of soil parameters: physical, chemical and biological ones. The literature compilation and survey is still undergoing as several reports have been only recently gathered in our hands. But as it is constituted, the data collection made so far reveals many complementary aspects of appraisal of agroforestry/shrub-based systems on soils state and resilience, which can now be used for a wide variety of impact assessment and processes inference, and ultimately for guiding the design of innovative ways of managing ligneous species in agricultural systems towards soil fertility resilience and sustainability.

Now 92 articles in which quantitative data could be extracted have been inserted into the database. The synergy perspective with WP4-5-6 is to be precised here.

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3. Dissemination activities related with the Deliverable

No dissemination activities initiated yet. Data collection and analysis are still progressing, and a publication will be made once all available literature will have been fully collected and properly analyzed. This will be published and advertised broadly. An update of the deliverable data file and report will be issued at that time for records.

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4. Appendix

The excel data file was given as a separate document and can be provided upon request

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